

Alkylations in Dimethylformamide

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The usual preparative procedure of *N*-phthalyl DL- β -phenylalanine involves a reaction between phenylalanine and phthalic anhydride. One of the classical methods for making *N*-phthalamido acids and free amino acids therefrom utilising Gabriel reaction is due to Sørensen¹. Our present work is essentially based on the Sørensen's scheme, but the preparative procedure have been significantly improved.

In recent years the use of dimethylformamide (DMF) as a solvent because of its high dielectric constant, excellent solvating and catalytic effect, has been extensive in synthetic and other applications. Its advantage in effecting different types of alkylation have been well established^{2,3,4}.

In the present work phthalimido was allowed to react directly with diethyl bromomalonate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dimethylformamide to afford diethyl phthalimidomalonate in 98% yield. The next sequence involves conversion of diethyl phthalimidomalonate to its sodium salt before effecting the reaction with the halo compound. The sodium salt was to be made absolutely alcohol free by heating at 145-155° at 15 mm for 8 hours⁵, otherwise the reaction would be sluggish. The reaction of diethyl phthalimidomalonate with benzyl chloride was however effected directly in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dimethyl formamide and the corresponding benzyl derivative was obtained in 76% yield. The method thus obviates the troublesome preparation of diethyl sodium phthalimidomalonate. The tricarboxylic acid obtained on saponification of diethyl phthalimido benzylmalonate was decarboxylated and cyclodehydrated in quantitative yield by heating the compound above its melting point.

Similar reaction of benzyl chloride with diethyl malonate gave diethyl benzylmalonate in 62% yield. The organic syntheses⁶ procedure also involves the initial formation of diethyl sodiomalonate and its reaction with benzyl chloride.

It would thus appear that the preparation of the sodium salt of malonic ester and its derivatives is unnecessary when the reaction is run in dimethylformamide and the process would thereby compete effectively with the other methods of preparation of *N*-phthalyl α -amino acids and the free α -amino acid therefrom.

1. *Chem. Zentr.*, 1903, 17, 33.

2. Bilman and Cash, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2499.

3. Zaugg *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 644.

4. Parker., *Quart. Rev.*, 1962, 16, 163 and the references cited therein.

5. *Organic Syntheses*, Coll. Vol. II, 1943 p. 384.

6. *Organic Syntheses*, Coll. Vol. III, 1955, p. 705.

Dimethylformamide was purified by shaking with solid potassium hydroxide and then distilling at atmospheric pressure⁷. The reactions in dimethylformamide were carried out under anhydrous conditions.

Diethyl phthalimidomalonate.—A mixture of diethyl bromomalonate (0.70 M, 168 g.), phthalimide⁸ (0.62M, 91g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.46M, 62g.) in dimethylformamide (350 ml) was stirred for 2½ hr. and then heated on a steam bath for another 2½ hr., when the evolution of CO₂ almost ceased. The solvent was then removed by distillation at reduced pressure and the residual mass was triturated with crushed ice. The solid residue was collected, boiled with benzene (300 ml.), cooled and filtered to remove unreacted phthalimide, if any. The benzene extract was distilled under reduced pressure to afford colourless diethyl phthalimidomalonate⁹, m.p. 71-72°; yield, 98%.

Diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate.—Freshly distilled benzyl chloride (0.327M, 37.5 ml.) was added to a mixture of diethyl phthalimidomalonate (0.295M, 90 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.103M, 22.5 g.) in dimethylformamide (225 ml.), and the whole stirred for 1 hr. at room temperature and then for 1½ hr. at 135-145°. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was triturated with crushed ice and the product was crystallised from ethanol, and had m.p. 109°, yield, 76%.

The compound remained unchanged on warming on a steam bath with 48% hydrobromic acid.

N-phthalyl-DL-β-phenylalanine.—A solution of sodium hydroxide (28 g.) in water (75 ml.) was added to a warm solution of diethyl phthalimidobenzylmalonate (71 g.) in ethanol (125 ml.) and heated under reflux for 1½ hr. on a steam bath. Water was added to the mixture to dissolve the separated solid, cooled, acidified to congo red and kept in a refrigerator overnight, when the benzyl o-carboxybenzamidomalonic acid crystallised out (52 g.), m.p. 159-162°. The tricarboxylic acid was decarboxylated and dehydrated in quantitative yield by heating just above its melting point and was found to be identical with a sample prepared according to Sheehan and Frank¹⁰.

Diethyl benzylmalonate.—Freshly distilled benzyl chloride (0.218 M, 25 ml.) was added to a well stirred mixture of diethyl malonate (0.2M, 32 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.148 M, 20.5 g.) in dimethylformamide (50 ml.) during 3 hr., the bath temperature being maintained at 140-145°. After maintaining at that temperature for an additional 30 min., the mixture was cooled, filtered and the inorganic salts were washed with fresh solvent. The combined filtrate was distilled at reduced pressure and the fraction distilling at 145-55°/5 mm. was collected: yield, 62%.

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10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1856.